

Knowledge, Attitude and Perception of the Population Related To Ebola Virus Disease in Kinshasa City, Democratic Republic Of The Congo

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ABSTRACT

Ebola Virus Disease (EVD) is an endemic zoonosis in tropical regions of Africa and Asia. Nowadays, this emerging and re-emerging disease is a serious public health problem. The present study was initiated to improve the level of knowledge and perception of the population on the EVD in Kinshasa. The survey was conducted among 254 households in Ngaba municipality located at Kinshasa city between 15 and 29 November 2014. The selection focused on this municipality is due to the fact that it was once hit by an epidemic. From identified among households, 249 were successfully surveyed, with a rate of 98%. Among the identified; we had 53.1% men and 46.9% women. It was noticed that 2% have never heard about EDV, 46.8% men and 39% women have a good knowledge of the EDV. Then 66.3% of the population would choose to call the health department if they were in front of a person with symptoms of EDV, and 98.8% perceive that the EVD is dangerous along with 67.9% are willing to help the Congolese authorities to educate the population to prevent it. Television was the most used source of information, either 88.4%. The present study highlights the lack of information and knowledge of the population in relation to the EVD. Many efforts are still required and significant investments are necessary for the dissemination of messages for the whole population. Such survey is reported for the first time in the Kinshasa city.

Keyword: *Ebola virus, Zoonosis, Ngaba commune, Kinshasa, Knowledge, Democratic Republic of the Congo*

INTRODUCTION:

Due to multiple health problems that the world is currently facing, especially in Africa, Ebola Virus Disease (EVD) is up-to-date. EVD appeared for the first time in 1976, when two simultaneous outbreaks took place in Nzara (Sudan) and Yambuku (Democratic Republic of the Congo). The great number of death occurred in Yambuku were reported to be due to Bolongo spirit totem from Ebola River (or Legbala located near Abumombazi city), and its name has been given to the disease [1]. Indeed, the Ebola term is the diminutive of the name Legbala. The water of this river would have been used by a lady Ngbandi originated from Abumombazi city (or Abuzi) which lived the city of Yambuku to throw a bad fate to the people who would have stolen and consumed her reserve of alcoholic drink and with their family (Congolese cultural and history) (aspects of EVD).

Many epidemics have stricken Africa and Asia and these in the past were sporadically caused by four different species of the virus, and were geographically distributed according to the viral strain causing the disease. Therefore, countries of Central, West and East Africa were affected by three virus strains (Zaire, Sudan and Ivory Coast); and the fourth strain (Reston) struck the United States of America and the Philippines [2].

Nowadays, five species were identified: Zaire, Bundibugyo, Sudan, Reston and Tai Forest. The first three have been associated with large outbreaks in Africa and Zaire is the virus responsible for the outbreak of 2014 in West Africa [3]. If the origin of the virus remains unknown, then the fruit bat will be considered as the natural host. The main suspected drivers of transmitting the disease are gorillas, chimpanzees and antelopes. Contamination from animals to humans is either by handling the meat of these infected animals or by consumption, especially in case of insufficient cooking. The Ebola virus belongs to the Filovirus family and it is one of the deadliest viruses in the world. In the ranking of biological pathogens, it is ranked 4th [4]. The current Ebola outbreak that struck the West Africa has been described by the World Health Organization (WHO) as the worst of all the time [5]. It should be noticed that in Africa, The Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) is the country struck a lot of times by this disease. The epidemic occurred in August 2014 in a landlocked area in the northwest of the country, within the Equatorial forest in Boende district (800 kilometers in the North-East of Kinshasa). And 60 registered cases, including 42 deaths, of which the mortality rate of about 60%, similar to that one observed in West Africa. However, contrary to West Africa, in DRC the situation

was quickly controlled. Not with standing, the Congo remains like all other countries of the world under the Ebola virus threat as it is the case in West Africa [6]. Hence, the need of thinking more on prevention than cure is necessary. Thus this prevention has to be through awareness but in taking into account the population perception level towards the EVD. The purpose of the current study was to assess the level of knowledge and perception of the population towards the EVD in Kinshasa, which is the second most populated city in Africa. The aim of this study is to determine the means by which the information reaches the public.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

This survey was conducted in Kinshasa city, Democratic Republic of the Congo, particularly in Ngaba municipality (fig. 1). This latter is located in the south of Kinshasa city in the Mont Amba district, with an area of 4 km² and a population estimated to 173,359 inhabitants in 2013. It is bounded to the North by Kikwit Street, to South and East by Bypass Avenue and Kalamu River and to the West by the University Avenue. It has six districts and 114 streets [7, 8].

Figure 1 (a): Study area location

Figure 1 (b): Residential areas and streets of the Ngaba municipality/commune (Source: Google Maps-©2014)

Study population

The study population consisted of 173,359 inhabitants, characterized by the following variables: age, sex, education level, profession, address and marital status.

Methodology

The Municipality/commune of Ngaba was selected randomly as a sample amongst all the municipalities of Kinshasa (Limete, Matete, Masina, Ngaba, Kalamu, Maluku and N'sele) in the past affected by the cholera epidemic [9, 10]. Surveys were carried out in 57 streets of Ngaba commune/municipality (50% of Ngaba total streets). This is a descriptive cross-sectional study based on a closed question questionnaire. It has five sections: Socio-demographic characteristics, general knowledge, attitudes, the perception and the means of the respondents.

Study period

The period of study was between November 2014 and March 2015 and occurred in two phases:

Pre-survey

The pre-survey was conducted in Mateba residential area and involved 50 people. It helped so much to unveil difficulties in understanding certain issues and has uncovered some unexpected aspects of the draft questionnaire. Thanks to that, our questionnaire has been reformulated.

Survey

It took place between 15 and 29 November 2014 (two weeks) and six residential areas were concerned. The information was collected using a pre-determined questionnaire.

Sample size determination

The selected sampling rate was 1/1000th, either a sample of 254 people instead of 173 for a good representation.

Inclusion criteria

- ❖ Live in the Municipality of Ngaba,
- ❖ Belong to the street randomly selected
- ❖ Belong to the compound randomly selected
- ❖ Belong to the household selected at random
- ❖ Accept to participate in the investigation
- ❖ For children, the consent of their parents or tutors was required.

The official statistics classifies 173,359 inhabitants of Ngaba commune into six residential areas as:

- ❖ Baobab residential area : 30 397 inhabitants ;
- ❖ Bulumbemba residential area : 22 581 inhabitants ;
- ❖ Luyi residential area: 35 044 inhabitants ;
- ❖ Mateba residential area: 19145 inhabitants ;
- ❖ Mpila residential area: 33 643 inhabitants ;
- ❖ Mukulwa residential area: 32549 inhabitants.

The same chance has been given to each participant of our main population to be included in the sample using Random sampling. In accordance with the subject of our main population random sampling has been used. Stratified random sampling helped for the determination of sample size by residential area, street and number of people to be interviewed by street.

Sample size determination by residential area

$$N_i = 250 \times N_q / N_c$$

Where:

N_i is the population size for i area in relation to the 250(n) people, N_q is the size of the population for each residential area and N_c is the size of the population throughout the Commune/municipality.

Determination of street number by residential area

$$N_n = 57 \times N_d / N_t$$

Where:

N_n is the number of streets by n selected residential areas related to the total number of streets, i.e. 57 streets, N_a is the number of street by residential area, and N_t is the total number of streets of Ngaba commune.

Determination of number of persons to interview by street

$$N_{na} = N_p / N_{aq}$$

Where:

N_{na} is the number of persons to interview by avenues, N_p is the number of persons for a chosen residential area and N_{aq} is the number of street for a chosen residential area.

Data collection

We carried out face-to-face interviews by using a protocol survey prepared for each investigator as well taking of households on the one hand; on the other hand this procedure was implemented for the survey, then a systematic awareness was conducted by investigators after each interview with the respondent.

The choice of streets to be investigated has been made by drawing lots without replacement. The chosen compound is the one which sum of digits gave an even number, in case where in a compound there were lots of households, the household whereby the participant is found has been chosen by a draw on the spot by investigators. If in that compound, nobody meets our inclusion criteria then we jump directly to the next compound. And if the selected household nobody meets our inclusion criteria, then the investigators are going to repeat the draw. By compound and household, only a person has been interviewed, and in each 2 compounds children have been interviewed. It has been planned reserved samples, and the interview was made by alternating gender. Investigators were divided into three groups each containing two investigators and each group had to investigate in two residential area. Each group was led by a supervisor. Having given the consent, then the investigator could start his/her interview.

Evaluation criteria on the knowledge of Ebola

Knowing the symptoms of EVD was calculated using a score evaluated from five symptoms known by the population

- ❖ A person without knowledge of the symptoms is the one who has not chosen any of the five symptoms.
- ❖ A person with a slight knowledge of the symptoms is the one who chose one or two of these symptoms.
- ❖ A person with an average knowledge of symptoms is the one who chose three or four symptoms.
- ❖ A person with a good knowledge of the symptoms is that chose all five symptoms.

Knowledge about the transmission of EVD was calculated using a score evaluated from four transmission means known by the population

- ❖ A person without knowledge on the means of transmission is the one that has not chosen means.
- ❖ A person with little knowledge of the means of transmission is the one who has chosen to only one means.

- ❖ A person with average knowledge of the transmission is the one that chose two to three means.
 - ❖ A person with a good knowledge of the means of transmission is the one who chose the four means.
- Knowledge on ways of preventing the EVD was calculated using a score evaluated from five known ways to prevent the population
- ❖ A person without knowledge of the means of prevention is one that has not chosen means.
 - ❖ A person with little knowledge of prevention methods is the one who chose a two means.
 - ❖ A person with average knowledge of the means of prevention is one that has chosen three to four means.
 - ❖ A person with a good knowledge about the means of prevention is one that has chosen every five ways.

Operational definitions

- ❖ Adult: is considered anyone who is 18 years old or more.
- ❖ Child or under age: anyone who is the range from 12 to 17 years old. This range of age is chosen because it requires a certain level of intelligence to respond the questionnaire.
- ❖ Face-to-face Interview: means the questionnaire is not given to the interviewee but rather it was the task of the investigator to read the questions.
- ❖ Gender Alternation: i.e. if the first to be interviewed is a male then the next one would be a female.
- ❖ Compound or plot : a portion of land
- ❖ Household: persons who constitute a family, living together and sharing the same food.

Data analysis

Data were collected using a questionnaire and entered with EPI Data software version 3.1. For further statistical analyses, Microsoft Office Excel 2007 and SPSS software version 19.0 were used. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean and qualitative variables as proportions and percentages.

RESULTS

The figure 1 shows that 11% of respondents only have heard about EVD and were informed that there was a phone number to the health service in case of emergency.

Figure 1 : Respondents knowledge about the existence of a free phone number of the health service in the event of onset of symptoms of EVD

Table 1 shows the percentage of women and men between 12-74 years old who have heard of Ebola virus disease, according to the socio-demographic characteristics.

Table 1: Participant who heard about EBOLA

Socio-demographic characteristics	Man (n=119)		Woman (n=135)		Total (n=254)	
	Heard about Ebola		Heard about Ebola		Heard about Ebola	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Age						

Child 12-17 years	44(37,0)	0(0,0)	45(34,6)	1(20,0)	89(35,9)	1(20,0)
Adult 18-74 years	75(63,0)	0(0,0)	85(65,4)	4(80,0)	160(64,1)	4(80,0)
Province						
Bandundu	85(71,4)	0(0,0)	80(61,5)	4(80,0)	165(66,3)	4(80,0)
Bas Congo	10(8,4)	0(0,0)	13(10,0)	1(20,0)	23(9,3)	1(20,0)
Equateur	4(3,4)	0(0,0)	12(9,2)	0(0,0)	16(6,4)	0(0,0)
Kasaï occidental	8(6,7)	0(0,0)	13(10,0)	0(0,0)	21(8,4)	0(0,0)
Kasaï oriental	8(6,7)	0(0,0)	5(3,8)	0(0,0)	13(5,2)	0(0,0)
Nord Kivu	1(0,8)	0(0,0)	1(0,8)	0(0,0)	2(0,8)	0(0,0)
Orientale	1(0,8)	0(0,0)	4(0,8)	0(0,0)	5(2,0)	0(0,0)
Kinshasa	2(1,7)	0(0,0)	1(0,8)	0(0,0)	3(1,2)	0(0,0)
Katanga	0(0,0)	0(0,0)	0(0,0)	0(0,0)	0(0,0)	0(0,0)
Marital status						
Single	83(69,7)	0(0,0)	77(59,2)	2(40,0)	160(64,3)	2(40,0)
Married	32(26,9)	0(0,0)	47(36,2)	2(40,0)	79(31,7)	2(40,0)
Divorced	2(1,7)	0(0,0)	1(0,8)	0(0,0)	3(1,2)	0(0,0)
Widow (er)	2(1,7)	0(0,0)	5(3,8)	1(20,0)	7(2,8)	1(20,0)
Education						
Uneducated	4(3,4)	0(0,0)	4(3,1)	0(0,0)	8(3,2)	0(0,0)
Educated	115(96,6)	0(0,0)	126(96,9)	5(100,0)	241(96,8)	5(100,0)
Profession						
Employed	41(34,5)	0(0,0)	31(23,8)	1(20,0)	72(28,9)	1(20,0)
Unemployed	78(65,5)	0(0,0)	99(76,2)	4(80,0)	177(71,1)	4(80,0)

It can be noticed that from Table 1, all men is 119 (100%) have heard about EVD against only 130 (96.3%) of women. They are mostly from Bandundu province, unemployed, educated, single, and adults.

The percentage of women and men who have certain knowledge on EVD is shown by Table 2.

Table 2: Knowledge on EVD symptoms, transmission and prevention

Knowledge on EVD	Man	Woman	Total n=249(100)
	n=119(47,8)	n=130(52.2)	
Knowledge on symptoms			
Fever	91(76,5)	92(70,8)	183(73,5)
Headache	70(58,8)	59(45,4)	129(51,8)
Diarrhea	97(81,5)	112(86,2)	209(83,9)
Vomiting	90(75,6)	85(65,4)	175(70,3)
Intense fatigue	76(63,9)	56(43,1)	132(53,0)
No knowledge	0(0,0)	0(0,0)	0(0,0)
Weak knowledge	32(26,9)	53(39,3)	85(33,5)
Average knowledge	36(30,3)	43(31,9)	79(31,1)
Enough Knowledge	51(42,9)	39(28,9)	90(35,4)
Knowledge on the transmission			
Contact with body fluids or secretions of an infected person	99(83,2)	94(72,3)	193(77,5)
To eat contaminated meats	98(82,4)	100(96,9)	198(79,5)
Contact with the corpse of someone dead from Ebola virus	99(83,2)	96(73,8)	195(78,3)
Improper hand hygiene	86(72,3)	99(76,2)	185(74,3)
No knowledge	0(0,0)	0(0,0)	0(0,0)
Weak knowledge	12(10,1)	23(17,0)	35(13,8)
Average knowledge	41(34,5)	52(38,5)	93(36,6)
Enough knowledge	66(55,5)	60(44,4)	126(49,6)
Knowledge on prevention			
Washing hands with clean water and soap	113(95,0)	123(94,6)	236(94,8)
Avoid any contact with an infected person	98(82,4)	97(74,6)	195(78,3)
Avoid eating bush meats	79(66,4)	95(73,1)	174(69,9)

Avoid any contact with a corpse of someone died from Ebola	93(78,2)	90(69,2)	183(73,5)
Avoid speaking to an infected person from Ebola	68(57,1)	76(58,5)	144(57,8)
Not enough knowledge	0(0,0)	0(0,0)	0(0,0)
Weak knowledge	21(17,6)	40(29,6)	61(24,0)
Average knowledge	48(40,3)	36(26,7)	84(33,1)
Enough knowledge	50(42,0)	59(43,7)	109(42,9)

It is clear from Table 2 that the respondents who have heard of the EVD have more knowledge about the transmission either 80.3% of men and 79.8% of women, followed by the knowledge on how to prevent EVD either 75.8% of men and 74% of women, then knowledge about the symptoms of EVD ranked last with 71.3% of men and 62.2% of women.

The attitude of men and women in front of a person presenting symptoms of EVD is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 : Participant attitude face to a person presenting EVD symptoms

	Man (n=119)		Woman (n=130)		Total (n=249)	
	Calling the health service	Others	Calling the health service	Others	Calling the health service	Others
Socio-demographic Characteristics						
Age						
Under age	33(38,8)	11(32,4)	29(36,2)	16(32,0)	62(37,6)	27(32,1)
Adult	52(61,2)	23(67,6)	51(63,8)	34(68,0)	103(62,4)	57(67,9)
Education						
Uneducated	2(2,4)	2(5,9)	2(2,5)	2(4,0)	4(2,4)	4(4,8)
Educated	83(97,6)	32(94,1)	78(97,5)	48(96,0)	161(97,6)	80(95,2)
Profession						
Employed	25(29,4)	16(47,1)	20(25,0)	11(22,0)	45(27,3)	27(32,1)
Unemployed	60(70,6)	18(52,9)	60(75,0)	39(78,0)	120(72,7)	57(67,9)

Other attitudes: to bring to the church, to a medical doctor or a traditional healer, to leave the infected person home and to carry to the hospital.

It is shown from Table 3 that 165 either 66.3% of respondents choose to call the health service and 84 either 33.7% of respondents will practice other attitudes if they were in front of a person with symptoms of EVD. Then 71.4% men and 61.5% women would call the health service.

The perception of respondents and their acceptance degree in order to help the authority to heighten the population for the prevention of EVD is shown in table 4.

Table 4: Perception of respondents on EVD

Perception of respondents on EVD	n=249	Percentage (%)
Is Ebola a dangerous disease?	246	98,8
Would you accept to help the government to heighten the population for the prevention of Ebola?	169	67,9

Table 4 shows that 246 respondents either 98.8% know that the EVD is dangerous and 169 respondents either 67.9% are willing to help the government to raise awareness to prevent EVD.

The percentage (%) of men and women in relation to sources of information on the EVD is described in table 5 below.

Table 5 : Respondent sources of information on EVD

Source of information	Man	Woman	Total
Radio	68(57,1)	59(45,4)	127(51,0)
TV	104(87,4)	116(89,2)	220(88,4)
Internet	21(17,6)	14(10,8)	35(14,1)
From a medical personnel	26(21,8)	34(26,2)	60(24,1)
From somebody's else	41(34,5)	62(47,7)	103(41,4)

Table 5 shows that television was the most used common source either 88.4% followed by radio either 51.1%. Women and men are most informed by television either 89.2% against 87.4%.

The percentage of participation of respondents in the awareness to prevent EVD related to some socio-demographic characteristics is presented in table 6.

Table 6: Participation of respondents in the awareness of the population to prevent Ebola

Socio-demographic Characteristics	Would you be willing to help the government to the awareness of the population in order to prevent Ebola		Total
	Yes	No	
Age			
Adult	105 (62,1)	55 (68,7)	160(64,3)
Under age	64(37,9)	25(31,3)	89(35,7)
Gender			
Man	80(47,3)	39(48,8)	119(47,8)
Woman	89(52,7)	41(51,2)	130(52,2)
Profession			
Unemployed	122(72,2)	55(68,7)	177(71,1)
Employed	47(27,8)	25(31,3)	72(28,9)
Marital status			
Widow/widower	6(3,6)	1(1,2)	7(2,8)
Divorced	2(1,2)	1(1,2)	3(1,2)
Married	48(28,4)	31(38,8)	79(31,7)
Single	113(66,8)	47(58,8)	160(64,3)
Education			
Educated	166(98,2)	75(93,8)	241(96,8)
Uneducated	3(1,8)	5(6,2)	8(3,2)

Table 6 shows that 67.9% of respondents would be willing to help the government to raise awareness to prevent EVD. Among them 62.1% are adults, 52.7% were women, 72.2% were unemployed, and 98.2% were educated.

DISCUSSION

The knowledge of population originated from Ngaba commune on EVD as well as mode of prevention, transmission and symptoms is an essential step in the process of struggle against the spread of this virus. Our investigation sought to assess this knowledge in the Congolese population, by asking a series of related issues. Then, we asked respondents if they had heard of the EVD and if they knew the means of transmission and possible ways to reduce the risk of contracting the virus. For the first time, EVD appeared in 1976, Nzara (Sudan) and Yambuku (DRC) [1]. In Sudan, the epidemic lasted five months and caused 151 deaths out of 284 cases (53% of mortality) [3] and from September to November 1976, the epidemic caused 280 deaths in DRC out of 318 registered cases (88% of mortality) [11]. We noticed that in 3 month epidemic; the rate of mortality in DRC is higher than that of Sudan (5 months epidemic). According to the latest WHO report, the outbreak rifting currently killed 5420 people, mostly in West Africa, out of a total of 15,145 infected patients [12]. The first known infection was the one that struck a little boy of two years in Guinea, but nowadays 2 134 cases have been identified and 1,260 deaths, with a mortality rate of about 59%. In Sierra Leone the assessment is of 6599 cases and 1398 deaths, either a mortality rate of 21.1%. In Liberia, the assessment is of 7168 cases and 3,016 deaths, either a mortality rate of 42 % [13]. In DRC, in the district of Boende (800 km north-east of the capital, Kinshasa), 70

cases and 42 deaths, either a mortality rate of 60% was recorded. It has to be noted that Boende is a small town in DRC where the population is below than the one of Kinshasa. The mortality rate recorded at Boende remains higher than the one recorded in Guinea, Sierra Leone and Liberia, although this epidemic has lasted only three months in this region of DRC unlike the one of West Africa is already approaching seven to eight months. The survey showed that almost all of the respondents have heard of the EVD. This could be due to the fact that DRC was stricken repeatedly by the epidemic. In general, 55.5% of men and 44.4% of women have a good knowledge of the means of transmission of Ebola virus; against 42.9% of men and 28.9% of women have good knowledge about the symptoms of EVD. It has been noticed that our study population has more knowledge about the means of transmission of the EVD than the knowledge about its symptoms. This is due to the fact that awareness (media) of the population had placed more emphasis on the means of transmission of Ebola virus.

In general, men have a good knowledge on the EVD compared to women either 46.8% or 39% respectively. This would be due to the fact that men are still coming out for the search of daily bread for their families, where they are in permanent contact with the society.

Regarding the attitude of respondents facing a person with symptoms of EVD, either 66.3% would choose to call the health service against 33.7% who could practice other attitudes. On the contrary, only 11% of respondents know the emergency call numbers of the health service in case of the manifestation of symptoms of EVD. This is significantly inadequate and it is due to the fact that the focus has not been on this emergency number and

this is dangerous in the fight against the spread of Ebola virus because the medical staff must be informed as soon as possible to prevent the spread and this is only possible from a phone call. At last, the perception of our respondents on the EVD is very high either 98.8% of respondents perceived that the EVD is dangerous. This is due to the virulence of this current epidemic in West Africa, and has produced more cases and deaths than the entire previous outbreaks gather together [1].

CONCLUSION

The aim of this survey was to evaluate the level of knowledge and perception of the population towards EVD. The study revealed that almost all of the respondents have heard about EVD but among them only 46.8% of men and 39% of women have got a good knowledge on EVD. It was noticed that 98.8% of the respondents perceive that EVD is dangerous and 67.9% are willing to help the government to raise awareness to prevent this disastrous disease. Television and radio are the main sources of information on EVD, either 88.4%. Results show also that the population has an insufficient level of knowledge about EVD. This situation is detrimental due to the severe and lethal nature of this epidemic, requiring a comprehensive and deep knowledge of EVD since a case of EVD can be fatal to an entire community. Our study confirms the interest of strengthening the awareness campaign near to that of the media. Such survey is reported for the first time in the Kinshasa city.

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